

DURABILITY OF SODA—LIME—SILICATE GLASSES. PART III.
RELATION BETWEEN ANNEALING AND CHEMICAL
DURABILITY

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The net effect of annealing on chemical durability of glass in bulk and the changes of chemical durability, when chilled glass is subjected to different temperatures for a specified period and to a definite temperature for varying periods, have been studied. Findings of Williams and Weyl have been verified by studying the effect of heat treatment on the surface durability.

The annealing of glass is a problem of profound practical importance and different investigations have contributed substantially towards its different aspects. Thus, some workers were interested in introducing suitable optical methods for detection and measurement of strain (Sir David Brewster, *Phil. Trans.*, 1814, 1815, 1816; Wilson, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1919, 3, 256; English, *ibid.*, 1919, 3, 258; Twyman, *ibid.*, 1917, 1, 67). The rate at which strain is removed from glass has been the subject of several studies (Preston, *Glass Ind.*, 1934, 15, 57; Littleton, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1933, 25, 748; Baily and Sharp, *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1933, 16, 367; Lillie, *ibid.*, 1936, 19, 45). Again a considerable amount of research work has been carried out of late years upon the relationship between the composition of a glass and its annealing temperature (English and Turner, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1918, 2, 90; 1919, 3, 278; 1920, 4, 387, 1921, 5, 115, 357; 1923, 7, 25, 73; 1924, 8, 173; Adams and Williamson, *J. Franklin Inst.*, 1920, 190, 597, 835; Valasek, U.S.A. Bureau of Standards, 1920, No. 358; Weidert, *Sprechsaal*, 1921, 54, 423; *Glashutte*, 1921, 51, 789, 803, 820; 1922, 52, 1, 17). Also, several investigators have shown that physical properties like density, coefficient of thermal expansion, specific heat, electrical properties, etc., are considerably modified as a result of annealing of glass (English and Turner, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1920, 4, 153; Tool and Eichlin, *J. Optical Soc. Am.*, 1924, 8, 419; *J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1925, 8, 1; Tool and Hill, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1925, 9, 185; Peters, Bureau of Standards, Scientific papers, 1926, No. 521; Wulff and Mazumdar, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, 31B, 319; Callender, *Trans. Roy. Soc.*, 1887, A, 178, 161; Holborn and Gruneisen, *Ann. Physik*, 1901, 6, 136; Turner and Winks, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1930, 14, 84).

Previous works, relating to the influence of heat treatment on chemical durability of glass, reveal that Keppeler (*Glasstech. Ber.*, 1927, 5, 97) was the first to point out the sharp distinction in respect of chemical resistivity between the surface of glass and its bulk. It was also pointed out that annealing not only removed mechanical stress, but that it also changed the constitution of glass. Similar work is that of Williams and Weyl (*Glass Ind.*, 1945, 26, 275, 325). In accordance with their findings the following changes are effected in glass, which has been subjected to annealing process: (i) Increased concentration of alkali at the surface, (ii) structural change, causing strengthening of the bond between the alkali ion and the anionic network, and (iii) removal of alkali from the surface by volatilisation and by its reaction with furnace gases.

The present work was undertaken with threefold objects : Firstly, to study the net effect of annealing on chemical durability of glass in bulk. Secondly, to make a systematic study of the change of chemical durability when a specimen of chilled glass is subjected to different temperatures for a specified period and to a definite temperature for varying period. Thirdly, to find out the effect of heat treatment on surface durability and thereby to verify the findings of Williams and Weyl (*loc. cit.*) in respect of alkali concentration at the surface.

It will be seen in the experimental portion that annealing substantially contributes towards increased durability of the glass in bulk and that there is an optimum temperature for each composition at which the maximum effect is obtained (Tables I, III & VII). It is, however, very doubtful if this increased durability is due mainly to a structural change which is expected to strengthen the bond between the alkali ion and the anionic network. The tendency of the alkali to migrate to the surface appears to be more even during annealing temperature range, provided the total surface area be large. Thus, under identical annealing temperature, the same glass gives divergent sulphuric acid values according as the glass is in the powdered or in the lump form. This will be evident from Table X. It has also been found that glass powder, which has been completely washed free of alkali, successively subjected to heat treatments, concentration of alkali at the surface in decreasing order is found to take place on each occasion. This continues for a number of times and ultimately ceases. But this aspect of the problem will form the subject matter of a subsequent communication.

As on previous occasions, the determination of the durability of glass was made by taking recourse to powder test (Faraday, *Phil. Trans.*, 1830, p. 49; Pelouze, *Compt. rend.* 1856, 43, 117; Mylius and Foerster, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1092; *Z. Instrum.*, 1889, 9, 120; Haumaier, *Met. Chem. Eng.*, 1917, 16, 604; Nicolardot, *Compt. rend.*, 1919, 169, 335; Peddl, *J. Soc. Glass. Tech.*, 1920, 4, 3, 299; 1921, 5, 72, 195).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

In order to test the net effect of annealing on durability of glass in bulk, bottles, both annealed and unannealed and prepared from the same melt, were procured from two different manufacturing firms. These bottles were subjected to powder test in the usual way. Table I embraces the results obtained with such bottles and Table II gives a complete analysis of unannealed specimen No. 2.

TABLE I

Source.	Type of glass.	Sulphuric acid values		
		Unannealed.	Annealed.	
Bharat Glass Works	Soda-lime-silicate	(i)	837	721
		(ii)	835	721
Glass Products Ltd.	Soda-lime-boro-silicate, No. 1	(i)	595	556
		(ii)	597	557
Do	soda-lime-boro-silicate, No. 2	(i)	535	462
		(ii)	536	462

It will be evident from Table I that annealing increases durability to a considerable extent.

TABLE II

Component	SiO ₂	R ₂ O ₃	CaO	B ₂ O ₃	Alkali*
% Composition	71.35	3.50	5.90	1.30	17.95
	(Total 100)				
By difference.					

With a view to studying the effect of varying temperatures on durability of glass, maintaining the duration of exposure constant, the unannealed specimen No.2 was broken into lumps of suitable sizes. About 20 g. of the broken lumps were taken for every experiment, each being done under identical conditions. The exposures to temperatures, varying between 100° and 700°, were given in an electrically heated muffle furnace, the temperature of which could be regulated properly. In each case, the furnace was raised to the desired temperature and then the charge was introduced in a platinum basin, the temperature maintained constant for 3 hours, and then allowed to fall slowly. As the furnace was properly insulated, the fall in temperature was a gradual one and required a period of 18 hours to attain room temperature. Up to 500° there was no deformity of the glass mass, but there was appreciable deformity, followed by fusion, at temperatures above 600°. After exposure, each batch was subjected to powder test and the results of such tests have been included in Table III.

TABLE III

Temp.	Exposed for	H ₂ SO ₄ value.	Temp.	Exposed for	H ₂ SO ₄ value.
Atmospheric (28°)	—	535	600°	3 hrs	(1) 425
100°	3 hrs.	512			(2) 426
200°	3	495			(3) 425
300°	3	485	700°	3	(1) 580
400°	3	481			(2) 579
500°	3	470			(3) 578

Table III shows that the sulphuric acid value gradually diminishes with the increase in temperature, attains a minimum value at 600°, and again increases as the temperature is further raised.

For obvious reason it was not possible to expose soda-lime-silicate glass to a temperature of 600° for annealing purpose. Naturally, to study the effect of time glass lumps were exposed to 500° for varying interval of time and the results of such treatments have been included in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Temp. = 500°.

Time (hrs.)	..	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
H ₂ SO ₄ value	..	482	477	470	456	435	427	425	425	425

Since in every case the rate of cooling was maintained constant, it appears from Table IV that for imparting maximum durability to a glass of fixed composition, the

duration of exposure should preferably be increased. The results of Table IV have been represented graphically in Fig. 1.

In order to corroborate further the observed effect of annealing, two new glasses of different compositions were melted and plained in different Morgan crucibles. Immediately after plaining they were withdrawn from the furnace so as to cool very rapidly. These specimens were next subjected to heat treatment. Table V shows the purity of the raw materials used, Table VI the percentage batch composition, and Table VII shows the effect of annealing at different temperatures.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

TABLE V

Material.	SiO ₂ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	CaO.	MgO.	Na ₂ O.	B ₂ O ₃ .	Loss.
Sand	97.2%	0.3%	1.8%	0.4%	Trace	—	—	0.3%
Lime	1.9	0.8	2.66	71.0	Trace	—	—	23.2
Soda ash	0.29	Nil	—	S. trace	S. trace	48.76%	—	14.2
Borax	0.08	Nil	S. trace	S. trace	S. trace	15.89	36.06	47.5

(as water)

TABLE VI

Batch No.	% Composition			
	SiO ₂ .	CaO.	Na ₂ O	B ₂ O ₃
a	73	9	18	—
	66	9.5	17.5	8.0

TABLE VII

Temp.	Duration.	Sulphuric acid value of batch	
		a.	b.
Ordinary (28°)	—	816	427
100°	3 hrs.	805	415
200°	3	800	405
300°	3	800	390
500°	3	795	351
600°	3	788	388
700°	3	795	390

If, however, a specimen of glass be brought to a desired temperature from a higher one, kept at that for 3 hours and then allowed to cool, the sulphuric acid value of the specimen is invariably slightly higher than that recorded previously. This will be clear from Table VIII, where each of the specimen was first raised to 700° and then brought to a particular temperature for usual annealing. For the sake of comparison the values obtained by direct heat treatment have also been incorporated in the table.

TABLE VIII

Duration=3 hours.

Batch No.	Temp.	Duration.	H ₂ SO ₄ value by heat treatment		Batch No.	Temp.	Duration.	H ₂ SO ₄ value by heat treatment	
			Direct.	Indirect.				Direct.	Indirect.
a	300°	3 hrs.	800	810	b	300°	3 hrs.	390	410
	500°		795	800		500°		351	380
	600°		758	770		600°		388	390
	700°		788			700°		390	

Fig. 2 gives a graphic representation of the data included in Tables I, III and VII.

To study the effect of heat treatment on surface durability, bottles of almost identical shape and capacity and prepared from the same melt, were procured from the previously mentioned firms. Each set comprised one annealed and one unannealed bottle. Each was filled with a definite volume of water and kept suspended in a water-bath, the level of water, both inside and outside the bottles, was maintained constant. The temperature of the water-bath was gradually raised to boiling and maintained at that for three hours. The whole was allowed to attain the room temperature slowly. Content of each bottle was taken in a previously treated conical flask and titrated with *N*/50-sulphuric acid. These results have been included in Table IX.

TABLE VIII

Source of glass bottle.	H ₂ SO ₄ required to neutralise the extract from	
	unannealed glass.	annealed glass.
Bharat glass Works	44.5 mg.	66.7 mg.
Glass Products Ltd.	5.0	7.5

The results shown in Table IX are in close agreement with the findings of Williams and Weyl (*loc. cit.*). But it is sufficiently clear that the tendency of alkali to migrate to the sur-

face is relatively high in soda-lime-silicate glass. As pointed out previously, the effect of constitutional changes during annealing appears to be less marked when the total surface area of the same glass is increased indefinitely. Thus, it will be seen from Table X that the net sulphuric acid value of the same glass is different according as the specimen is annealed in the lump or in the powdered form. The glass was powdered to pass 160 mesh sieve.

TABLE X

Batch No.	Annealing temp.	Duration.	H ₂ SO ₄ value	
			Lump.	Powdered.
a	500°	3 hrs.	795	885
b	500°	3	351	373

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